

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

LEXICAL AND SYNTACTICAL STYLISTIC DEVICES BASED ON REPETITION

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Abstract

The article elaborates the difference between similar lexical and syntactical devices which are based on repetition. Similar and distinctive points of some different rhetoric devices have been studied in the article. Lexical and syntactical devices such as epistrophe or anaphora, mesodiplosis, epiphora, symploce, epizeuxis, parallel construction, reversed construction or chiasmus, antimetabole, anadiplosis, antistasis, negative-positive restatement, diacope and gradatio, epanalepsis have been analyzed respectively. While analyzing the terms which are based on the repetition, it turned out that the major goal of these devices is the emphasis. Despite one common feature, these rhetoric devices and techniques differ from each other for the location along or inside the sentence(s) or clause(s). So some of them are repeated at the beginning of the sentence (epistrophe) while the others are found at the end (epiphora) and in the middle (mesodiplosis) of the sentence or clause. Some are repeated within two or more clauses or sentences in different places.

Keywords: gradatio, antistasis, chiasmus, diacope, mesodiplosis, antimetabole, epanalepsis

The article studies repetition which can occur through morphological and syntactical repetitions. These types of repetitions include epistrophe or anaphora, mesodiplosis, epiphora, symploce, epizeuxis, parallel construction, reversed construction or chiasmus, antimetabole, anadiplosis, antistasis, negative-positive restatement, diacope and gradatio, epanalepsis, etc.

First of all, we had better pay attention to epistrophe which is the repetition of some specific words or a word at the end of successive clauses, phrases or sentences. This is considered to be a morphological repetition. For example; For no government is better than the men who compose it and I want the best and we need the best and we deserve the best.

Analyzing the afore-mentioned example we see both epistrophe and parallelism here especially after the conjunction "and". Another name of epistrophe is epiphora which is usually found at the end of clauses, sentences or phrases. This rhetorical device is usually found in poems to generate rhythms. But they can also be seen in prose; "See no evil, hear no evil, speak no evil".

The next rhetorical device which produces repetition is anaphora. Anaphora is a stylistic device in which a word or a phrase is repeated at the beginning of successive sentences or clauses. Its main goal is to create emphasis. Anaphora is an incredibly strong mnemonic device which mainly poets use in their poems.

Mesodiplosis is the repetition of a word in middle of a clause or sentence. Repetition may occur within two or more successive sentences. It is a word of Greek origin which means "mesos" and "a doubling". Mesodiplosis is usually seen in poems. It is rarely seen in everyday speech. For example,

We are troubled on every side, yet not distressed;

We are perplexed, but not in despair;

Persecuted, but not forsaken;

Cast down, but not destroyed. (Corinthians 4:8-9).

Another figure of speech which is based on repetition is symploce, This is syntactical stylistic device because it is observed along and inside two or more successive sentences or clauses. This rhetoric device is made up of the combination of epistrophe and anaphora. But it does not mean that it is mesodiplosis. The word "symploce" is of Greek origin which means "interweaving" [10]. For instance, Ex president of the USA said: "When there is a talk of hatred, let us stand up and talk against it. When there is talk of violence, let us stand up and talk against it".

Epizeuxis is a rhetoric device based on repetition in which a word is repeated in an immediate sequence, mainly within the same sentence, for emphasis or vehemence . [1]. It is usually used to create an emotional appeal to stimulate the audience. Herewith, epizeuxis may also be employed to create a comic effect. Epizeuxis may appear within one sentence and two or more sentences. It means that epizeuxis is considered to be both morphological and syntactical repetitions. Writers [6]. For example, Our top priority was, is and always will be education, education, education [4].

Parallel construction consists of phrases or words which are repetitions among adjacent clauses or sentences [7]. The most specific feature of parallel construction is that similar or identical syntactical structure is observed in two or more successive sentences. Parallel constructions are mainly accompanied with the repetition of conjunctive words and preposition. Parallel construction is also called parallel syntax. Clauses or sentences are repeated to underline the central theme or idea that the author is going to convey. Parallelism is the sign of a perfect language speaker [9]. Another name of parallel syntax is parallel sentence structure. This stylistic device facilitates the flow of a sentence. It also helps making the sentence more brief by removing needless words which can distract the reader from the central idea. It is a common way of clarifying and

avoiding ambiguity, but it is avoided unless the relationship of the details or ideas that they express justifies parallelism [5]. Parallel structure looks like the derived conjunction analysis, as it assumes some fundamental complete sentences.

Apart from providing emphasis, it is obvious that parallelism appeals to the listener or reader in different ways, too. Before all, repetition of clauses develops profound mental ability to process the sentence as a whole. Researches have revealed that the reiteration of the second clause will raise the speed that a person can process the sentence. Moreover, it alleviates the extra information necessary to be processed by the reader, facilitating comprehension. Since it is more appealing and convincing. [8].

Persuasion appears through parallel syntax through repetition. Paired phrases, clauses and sentences should be formed with equal structure according to noun or verb choice. In this case the number of meters and syllables. We can also see the term "faulty parallelism" which is accompanied with coordinating conjunctions that connect adjectives and nouns [12]. When we use parallel syntax between two clauses, it is called "isocolon". When there are 3 clauses, it is known as "tricolon".

Similar syntactical structures among phrases and sentences help to determine the proximity of the ideas suggested within them [11]. Isocolon derives from the Greek words iso (equal) and kolon (member). Hence each clause is usually the same length. But the same rule cannot be referred to a tricolon which is composed of 3 clauses. Tricolons can be in different lengths.

Parallel construction is often used in anaphora, epistrophe, antithesis, asyndeton, climax, symproce [3]. In general, they are accompanied with repeated conjunctions or words.

Reversed Construction is also called chiasmus. Chiasmus is a rhetoric device in which grammatical structures are repeated in reverse order. Therefore, this stylistic device has also been included in the classification of stylistic devices based on repetition. In stylistics, chiasmus is derived from ancient Greek which means "to shape like the letter X". It is a reversal of grammatical constructions in successive phrases or clauses. Unlike grammatical structures, words are not repeated in chiasmus. There is a balance between phrases or words with similar meanings. But they are not completely identical. For example;

We were elected to change Washington, and we let Washington change us.

Antimetabole resembles to chiasmus in terms of having the feature of repetition. But unlike chiasmus, repetition of both grammatical structures and words is seen in successive clauses or phrases which are in the shape of A-B-B-A. For instance;

Pleasure is a sin and sometimes sin is a pleasure.

Antimetabole and chiasmus reinforce antithesis. Sometimes, the repetition is not seen in grammatical structures or words.

Repetition can sometimes be seen in meaning, particularly when the words are in an opposed sense. Antistasis is a stylistic device which emerges as a result of a repetition of a word or phrase in a different or contrary

sense. Antistasis expresses contrastive difference between meanings. This stylistic device is also called antanadasis. It is a strong rhetoric device which has been used in the poems of poets for a long time. The repetition is done in order to provide emphasis or to arrange the rhymes in the poems. For example, Nothing can be made out of nothing (William Shakespeare, King Lear).

There is also a similar rhetoric device called anadiplosis. Anadiplosis is also of a Greek origin meaning "doubling" or "repetition". It is a syntactical stylistic device in which the last word or phrase of one sentence, clause or line is repeated at the beginning of the next clause or sentence which is usually split by comma or slash. Gradatio is considered to be an extended anadiplosis. Gradatio is described as the climbing or marching rhetoric device. Comparing chiasmus and anadiplosis, Javid Babayev underlines: "the word order is just repeated without changing the order of words or a group of words in anadiplosis though the meanings of words are opposed and generate antithesis in chiasmus" [2, p.116]. a good example for anadiplosis is shown below;

Hard times create strong men. Strong men create good times. Good times create weak men. And the weak men create hard times. (Michael Hopf, Those who remain).

When studying the rhetoric devices creating repetition, it is a method of making emphasis by underlying the idea twice. The idea is repeated first in negative terms, then in positive terms. A negative-positive re-statement repeats an idea in a similar sentence but changes it to make a contrast. Actually, it looks like antimetabole to some extent. For example, Ask not what your country can do for you; ask what you can do for your country.

Diacope is a literary device which occurs with the deliberate repetition of words such as "to be or not to be". This technique is usually used by writers and poets in prose, poetry and dialogue to form clarity and rhetorical effect. Diacope is of Greek origin which means "to cut into two". Diacope resembles to epanalepsis in form. The difference between epanalepsis and diacope is that epanalepsis shows up when the same initial phrase or word is repeated after up to 3 intervening words.

Epanalepsis is a rhetoric device in which the beginning of sentence or clause is repeated at the same sentence or clause with intervening words.

Overall, it is possible to come to such a conclusion that all the rhetoric devices and techniques scrutinized above have one denominator- having the feature of emphasis.

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